

Australian Microbiome

Advancing environmental microbiome science through FAIR and standardised (meta)data

Andrew Bissett | April 2026

Australia's National Science Agency

UNOFFICIAL

What is Australian Microbiome?

An open (Australian) microbiome discovery platform, enabling discovery of microbial diversity across a geographically expansive and diverse range of Australian terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. The AM delivers FAIR data on the occurrence and distribution of potential microbiological resources, collated into a searchable public database that will allow researchers and other end-users to address a broad variety of questions in microbial ecology.

UNOFFICIAL

UNOFFICIAL

Australian Microbiome Core TEAM

Jodie Van De Kamp

Sophie
Mazard

Dean Rollins

Matt Smith

QCIF – Mark Terle, Bigette Gonch

UNOFFICIAL

The Australian Microbiome project unites isolated efforts into a coordinated, FAIR-compliant ecosystem

Evolving from earlier initiatives like BASE and Marine Microbes (2012–2018), the AM project provides a focal point for engagement with global microbiome communities.

Standardization

Enforces global standardization of methods, protocols, metadata, and analysis. Methods compliance is highly highly encouraged, while rich metadata compliance is mandatory.

FAIR Access

Guarantees Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable access to primary sequence data and derived data products.

Analytical Pathways

Provides web-based data portals, GitHub workflows, and direct links to Galaxy Australia for data exploration and analysis.

BASE

Marine Microbes

Independent Studies

Global Standards

Global Repositories

Global Community

Why the Need? The Challenge of Data Silos

The Data Sharing Gap

Scientific communities generally struggle with efficient and transparent data sharing practices.

Single-Study Limitations

Most collected data is currently restricted to a single study or application.

Limited Inference Base

Fragmented data denies the development of novel applications and broad scientific insights.

Work / Technology & tools

TAKING THE PAIN OUT OF DATA SHARING

Despite agreeing to make raw data available, some authors fail to comply. The right strategies and platforms can ease the task. By Matthew Hutson

Create a global microbiome effort

Understanding how microbes affect health and the biosphere requires an international initiative, argue Nicole Dubilier, Margaret McFall-Ngai and Liping Zhao.

“There are two major stumbling blocks to advancing our understanding of microbes' role in the biosphere. First is the fragmentation of the life-sciences field. Second is a lack of coordination among the various microbiome research endeavours under way”

Vision

To unite data, people, and ideas in support of (environmental) microbiome-led innovation and discovery, in an Australian context.

Mission

- Sustain and strengthen the Australian environmental microbial genomic resource
- Engage a broad range of end users and improve collaboration between microbiome researchers in different research fields
- Enable and encourage greater communication and collaboration among people interested in microbiomes
- Enhance functionality to allow translation of the resource for applied outcomes and foster innovative research

THREE OPTIONS FOR AUSTRALIAN MICROBIOME SAMPLING

1 RANDOM SAMPLING (Darts-at-a-Map Approach)

Samples placed without plan, potentially leaving gaps in critical areas.

Summary: sporadic sampling points, gaps

2 GRADIENT-TARGETED SAMPLING (Environmental Coverage)

- Central Desert
- Northern Tropical Rainforest
- Southern Temperate Forest
- Coastal Fringe

SYSTEMATIC COVERAGE of diverse ecosystems and climate gradients.

Summary: strategic coverage of environmental diversity

3 DECENTRALIZED ENABLEMENT (Local Researcher Network Approach)

EMPOWERING LOCAL INDIVIDUAL RESEARCHERS, collectively building broader coverage through local enablement.

Summary: distributed network of local projects

3 DECENTRALIZED ENABLEMENT (Local Researcher Network Approach)

EMPOWERING LOCAL INDIVIDUAL RESEARCHERS, collectively building broader coverage through local enablement.

Summary: distributed network of local projects

- Only model that wasn't merely building a single use dataset
- Mission and vision statement have user engagement focus
- Sample selection guided by user input, environmental gradients, geographic and temporal coverage

~50 contributing "entities"
Many more individuals

International:

European Bioinformatics Initiative

Global Soil Biodiversity Initiative

Earth Microbiome Project

TARA Oceans

University of Auckland

Edith Cowan University

Murdoch University

Dept. of Bio diversity, Conservation and Attractions

Kings Park Botanical Gardens

Iron Range Research Station (Maxim Foundation)

Australian Institute of Marine Science

James Cook University

Director of National Parks Australia

GeoScience Australia

Science Investment Endowment fund

Atlas of Living Australia

National Soils Archive

Dept. of Energy and the Environment

Grains R&D Corporation

Bush Blitz

University of Adelaide

Terrestrial Eco system Research Network

CSIRO

Australian Research Data Capability

Sugarcane R&D Corporation

University of Queensland

University of Newcastle

Bioplatforms Australia

Macquarie University

University of Western Sydney

Sydney Institute of Marine Science

University of Technology

University of NSW

Ramaciotti Centre for Genomics

Australian Genome Research Facility

Australian National Data Service

La Trobe University

Vic. Dept. of Economic Development

Royal Botanical Gardens Melbourne

The University of Melbourne

Deakin University

Forestry Tasmania

Integrated Marine Observing System

Australian Antarctic Division

Tasmanian Land Conservancy

University of Tasmania

CORE FUNDING PARTNERS

- Soil
- Water
- Host
- Coastal/sediment
- Time Series

Soils = 2 depths
Water = > 1 Depth (6-9)

~14,000 samples
~2,500 shotgun metagenomes

AM = co-ordinated microbiome effort

UNOFFICIAL

Resources microbiome data collection/generation:

- Standardises methods, metadata, analysis
 - Methods compliance ‘encouraged’, metadata compliance mandatory
 - Github, web-based documentation
- Provides FAIR access to primary data and derived data products
 - Web based data portals
 - Amplicon and shotgun Metagenomes, Transcriptomes
 - Rich metadata
- Provides access to data exploration and analysis “pathways”
 - Web based data portals, links to Galaxy Australia, github for workflows
- Provides focal point for engagement with global microbiome (and other) communities
 - Federation of workflows / analysis pathways
 - Global standardisation of methods, protocols, metadata
 - Integration and interoperability of data

UNOFFICIAL

A decade of continuous observation has yielded an unprecedented scale of environmental data.

> 10 Years

of continuous data collection (including IMOS time series extending ~10 years, monthly, at 3-6 depths).

> 14,000 Samples

spanning Soil, Water, Host, and Coastal/sediment environments.

> 50,000

Sequence Datasets (averaging 3-5 datasets per sample).

> 100 Billion

Sequences generated.

> 30,000

MAGs (Metagenome-Assembled Genomes) compiled.

93 Million+

Occurrences mobilized through GBIF.

■ Yes ■ No

Do you know what Australian Microbiome (AM) is?

52%

48%

Have you submitted samples to AM before?

16%

84%

Have you downloaded data from AM before?

24%

76%

■ Yes, MiXs ■ Yes, DwC ■ Yes, other ■ No

Do you use standardised metadata when you conduct microbiome research?

16%

20%

64%

Yes, a sequence repository (e.g. NCBI, ENA) Yes, an occurrence repository (e.g. ALA, GBIF) No

Do you submit microbiome data to a data repository?

40%

60%

Yes, successfully Yes, unsuccessfully No

Have you ever tried to re-use some one else's data?

48%

52%

Yes No

Have you ever collected metagenomic data in a pilot context to better design an experiment / survey?

48%

52%

OPTIONAL: If yes, did you try and find data for this in a public repository?

39%

61%

UNOFFICIAL

Microbiome Data

Microbiome

Microbiota

Bacteria

Archaea

Fungi

Protists

Algae

+ “Theatre of activity”

Microbial structural elements

 Proteins/
peptides

Lipids

 Poly-
sacharides

 Nucleic acids
structural DNA/RNA

 mobile genetic elements
incl. viruses/phages relic DNA

Internal/external structural elements

 Environmental
conditions

Microbial metabolites

 Signalling
molecules

Toxins

 (An)organic
molecules

Biome: a reasonably well defined habitat which has distinct bio-physio-chemical properties

- Environmental conditions:
 - Edaphic / Pelagic variables
 - Climate
 - Other biodiversity

Australian Microbiome data

Primary data Derived data

- **FASTQ**
- Feature tables
- Assemblies/annotations
- **Metadata** (sample specific (contextual), assay, experimental etc)

Standardisation through best practice and Metadata

Toward a Global Public Repository of Community Protocols to Encourage Best Practices in Biomolecular Ocean Observing and Research

Robyn M. Samuel^{1,2*}, Raissa Meyer³, Pier Luigi Buttigieg⁴, Neil Davies⁵, Nicholas W. Jeffery⁶, Christopher Meyer⁷, Christina Pavlouidi⁸, Kathleen Johnson Pitz⁹, Maxime Sweetlove¹⁰, Susanna Theroux¹¹, Jodie van de Kamp¹² and Alison Watts¹³

STANDARDISATION

UNOFFICIAL

Integrated, not merely aggregated, data

UNOFFICIAL

Microbiome Experiments

Curated FAIR Data & Metadata

Scalable ML

The screenshot shows the data portal interface for the Australian Microbiome Initiative. The search bar contains the text "sample_id: 102.100.100/7031". Below the search bar, there are 7 datasets found for the search term. The first dataset is "BASE Metagenomics 7031_1" with a size of 1.92 GiB. The "Bulk download (metadata and data)" button is highlighted with a red circle. The first dataset entry is also circled in red.

Primarily useful for:

1. sequence data (fastq)
2. Full metadata

Search over any metadata field

Bulk download (metadata and data)

Download data

Inspect dataset

Organizations The Australian Microbiome Initiative

Map Contextual data Sequence data Processed data

Cancel membership

Search by:

sample_id: 102.100.100/7031

7 datasets found for "sample_id: 102.100.100/7031" Order by: Relevance

External Data Linkage

BASE Metagenomics 7031_1
Woomeera, MiSeq 18S
1.92 GiB [View Cart](#)

BASE Amplicons ITS 7031_1 A45H
Woomeera, Sanger
18.95 MiB [View Cart](#)

BASE Amplicons A16S 7031_1 A480G
Woomeera, MiSeq 4185
50.2 GiB [View Cart](#)

BASE Amplicons 16S 7031_1 A489J GA19GCTCTA
Woomeera, Sanger
60.12 MiB [View Cart](#)

BASE Amplicons 16S 7031_1 A489J GA48AAGCGGTA
Woomeera, Sanger
51.37 MiB [View Cart](#)

BASE Amplicons 16S 7031_1 A491C
Woomeera, Sanger
60.53 MiB [View Cart](#)

UNOFFICIAL

BASE Metagenomics 7031_1

Followers
0

Follow

Organization

The Australian Microbiome Initiative

Supporting Information

Initiative Information

Methods

Data Policy

Acknowledgement and Citations

External Data Linkages

NCBI Bioproject (Organisation) - PRJNA507010

NCBI Bioproject (Dataset) - PRJNA317932

License

CC-BY-4.0-AU

BASE Metagenomics 7031_1

Woomeera, MiSeq 18S

Dataset size is 1.92 GiB

Bulk download (metadata and data)

View Cart

Add

Data and Resources

7031_1_PE_S50bp_BASE_UNSW_H9WYBCOX_GAATTCGT-AT... (458.18 MiB) [Access](#)

7031_1_PE_S50bp_BASE_UNSW_H9WYBCOX_GAATTCGT-AT... (524.74 MiB) [Access](#)

7031_1_PE_S50bp_BASE_UNSW_H9WYBCOX_GAATTCGT-AT... (518.07 MiB) [Access](#)

7031_1_PE_S50bp_BASE_UNSW_H9WYBCOX_GAATTCGT-AT... (465.48 MiB) [Access](#)

BASE_metagenomics_UNSW_H9WYBCOX_checksums.md5 (13.18 KiB) [Access](#)

This data is made available openly under a Creative Commons Attribution license. Please see the Initiative Data Policy for attribution information.

Soil metagenomics

Show Blank Fields

Additional Info

Field	Value
Geospatial Coverage	<p>Dataset extent</p> <p>Map data © Data by OpenStreetMap, under CC BY SA</p>
Resource Permissions	organization_member_after_embargo:archive_ingestion_date:30am-consortium-members
Access Control Date	2015-10-20
Access Control Mode	date
Sequence Data Type	illumina-shortread
am_environment	Soil
ammonium_nitrogen_wt (mg/kg)	4.0
ammonium_nitrogen_wt_meth	meth_2_1
analysis_software_version	1.8.2
archive_ingestion_date	2015-07-22
bioplatforms_project	Biome of Australia Soil Environments (BASE)
biotic_relationship	Free-living
boron_hot_cac2 (mg/kg)	2.65
boron_hot_cac2_meth	meth_2_1
clay (%)	31.06
clay_meth	meth_2_1
coarse_sand (%)	19.87
coarse_sand_meth	meth_2_1
collection_date	2011-10-30T00:00:00
color	BROR
conductivity (dS/m)	2.349
conductivity_meth	meth_2_1
data_generated	2015-07-22

UNOFFICIAL

Processed Data Portal

UNOFFICIAL

<https://data.bioplatforms.com/bpa/otu>

Amplikon Metagenome Contextual Map

Home Australian Microbiome Home andrew.bawen@csiro.au

Filter by amplikon, taxonomy and traits

Amplikon 279519_bacteria

Taxonomy

Domain

Phylum

Class

Order

Family

Genus

Species

Trait

Clear

Contextual Filters

Environment

Contextual Filters

More than one filter may be used and combined with "all/any" functions. The sample integrity warnings filter will be applied in addition to other contextual filters.

Uncheck to remove samples with integrity warnings

Add Clear

Simple search BLAST search Interactive map search Interactive graph search Interactive sample comparison

Download Contextual Data only (CSV) Download OTU and Contextual Data (CSV) Download BIOM format (Pyrch compatible) Export Data to Galaxy Australia for further analysis Export Data to Galaxy Australia for Krone Taxonomic Abundance Graph

Please use the search button to start your search

Sample ID	Environment	Krona Plot
No search performed yet		

Page 1 of 1 10 rows

Filter by amplicon, taxonomy and traits

Amplicon

Taxonomy

Select Amplicon to filter taxonomy, or

Taxonomy

Domain

Phylum

Class

Order

Family

Genus

Species

Trait

Clear

Contextual Filters

Environment

Contextual Filters

More than one filter may be used and combined with "all/any" functions.
The sample integrity warnings filter will be applied in addition to other contextual filters.

Uncheck to remove samples with integrity warnings

Add

Clear

Interactive Map Search

Showing 9508 samples in 1041 sample locations

Filter by amplicon, taxonomy and traits

Amplicon

Taxonomy

Select Amplicon to filter taxonomy, or [Search for a taxonomy](#)

Taxonomy	silva132 wang	
Domain	is	d_Bacteria
Phylum	is	p_Proteobacteria
Class	is	c_Alphaproteobacteria
Order	is	o_SAR11_clade
Family	is	---
Genus	is	---
Species	is	---

Sample ID

138454

138455

138456

138457

138458

138459

138460

138461

138462

138463

Interactive Map Search

Showing 9508 samples in 1041 sample locations

g_Thiospont_unclassified 0.00%
 g_Ekaryota_unclassified 0.00%
 Species: 0%

Dissimilarity method: Bray-Curtis

Env Local Scale

UMAP parameters:

View

Samples: 364

Marker size:

Download

N/A

1.1.6 Protected landscape

1.3.3 Residual native cover

1.1 Nature conservation

1.1.7 Other conserved area

2.1.0 Grazing native vegetation

1.1.1 Strict nature reserve

1.2.1 Biodiversity

2.2.1 Wood production

1.1.3 National park

1.2.2 Surface water supply

6.5.1 Marsh/wetland—conservation

1.1.5 Habitat/species management area

1.3 Other minimal use

Any contextual filter

Amplicon <is> 27f519r_bacteria

Taxonomy <is> silva138 SKlearn

Domain <is> d_Bacteria

Phylum <isnot> d_Bacteria_unclassified

Vegetation Type <contains> Dune

Vegetation Type <contains> Marsh/bog

Vegetation Type <contains> Mangrove

Vegetation Type <contains> Forest

The download provides: 1) the blast search details, 2) the blast table results, 3) a table with hit sequences, their match details, their locations and sample attributes, and 4) a map showing hit locations and sequence similarities.

Note that the figure is sorted to plot the highest scoring points last, so any symbols occurring at the same location will only be visible as the highest scoring alignment value.

Search Parameters

qcov_hsp_perc ⓘ

60 ▾

perc_ident ⓘ

95 ▾

```
CTGTTGCCAGGGGAAGAACGTCTTGTAGAGTAACTGCTACAAGAGTGACGGTACCTGAGAAGAAGCCCGGCTAACTACGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATACGTAGGGGGCAAGCGTTGTC  
GGAATTATTGGCGTAAA
```

BLAST search executed successfully. Click [here](#) to download the results.

Some examples of data usage

- Soil related

- Methods related

- Marine related

UNOFFICIAL

ARTICLE IN PRESS

Communications Earth & Environment <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-026-03398-y>

Article in Press

Decoding bacterial and fungal richness with autoencoders yields a unified ratio indicating soil health and ecological susceptibility

Received: 9 September 2025

Accepted: 4 March 2026

Raphael A. Viscarra Rossel, Thorsten Behrens, Andrew Bissett, Lewis Walden & Mingxi Zhang

UNOFFICIAL

Decoding the Soil at Continental Scale

Fusing mid-infrared spectroscopy with deep learning to translate localized samples into a unified national map.

1. Ground Truth

482 physical soil samples (0-10 cm depth) sequenced to identify distinct bacterial and fungal taxa.

2. Spectral Expansion

Mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy translates the DNA data, confidently predicting microbial richness across an additional 2,850 geographic sites.

3. The AI Engine

Deep supervised autoencoders ingest dozens of complex, interacting variables (climate, topography, mineralogy, land-use) and compress them to discover hidden ecological rules.

4. Causal Inference

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) acts as the final interpretive layer, untangling direct and indirect environmental effects.

Divergent Kingdoms: Bacteria vs. Fungi

Explainable AI reveals that bacteria and fungi are governed by entirely different environmental filters and spatial scales.

Fungi (The Specialists)

Spatial Range
Short and Local
(28 km radius).

Primary Drivers

Autumn vapor pressure, Total Organic Carbon (TOC), and dense vegetative productivity.

Ecological Strategy

Highly specialized. Sensitive to local micro-climates and heavily dependent on stable, plant-associated resources. Promotes carbon storage.

Bacteria (The Adaptors)

Spatial Range
Broad and Regional
(72 km radius).

Primary Drivers

Topographic complexity (slope/elevation), Total Nitrogen, and Aridity.

Ecological Strategy

Highly adaptable and copiotrophic. Thrives in highly variable, topographically complex, disturbed, or arid conditions. Promotes rapid nutrient turnover.

The Unified Metric: The B:F Richness Ratio

By dividing bacterial by fungal richness, a new, spatially explicit indicator of microbial community balance emerges.

High B:F Ratio (Bacterial Dominance)
Where: Arid and semi-arid interiors, heavily managed lands, low-input soils.
Drivers: Extreme aridity and high soil pH.

Low B:F Ratio (Fungal Dominance)
Where: Cooler, wetter coastal zones, tropical norths, and organic-rich forests.
Drivers: Consistent moisture and high organic carbon availability.

The Insight

This single ratio successfully integrates complex climate, vegetation, and soil variables into a unified, scalable heat-map of ecological state

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Soil Biology and Biochemistry

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/soilbio

Short Communication

Alpha-diversity is strongly influenced by the composition of other samples when using multiplexed sequencing approaches

Andrew Bissett^{a,*}, Mark V. Brown^b^a CSIRO Oceans and Atmosphere, Hobart, Tasmania, Australia^b School of Environmental and Life Sciences, University of Newcastle, Callaghan, New South Wales, Australia

UNOFFICIAL

- Cross talk Always occurs, most evident around detection limit
- Changing a zero to another number is bad for diversity estimates
- Important to know what else was sequenced on your run (metadata!)
- Comparing alpha diversity between runs and specific samples can be difficult
- In larger context of diversity and patterns things seem more robust

communications biology

ARTICLE

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-05702-4>

OPEN

A marine heatwave drives significant shifts in pelagic microbiology

Mark V. Brown ¹,
Matthew C. Smith¹, Andrew Bissett ¹

Community Temperature Index

UNOFFICIAL

UNOFFICIAL

IMOS Integrated Marine Observing System

Biological Ocean Observer

IMOS Integrated Marine Observing System
Biological Ocean Observer

Home EOVs **Microbes** Phytoplankton Zooplankton Larval Fish Environmental Data Relationships Information

Time Series NRS Time Series Coastal Voyage data

Note: Hover cursor over circles for station name

Select a station:

- Darwin
- Port Hacking
- Yongala
- Kangaroo Island
- North Stradbroke Island
- Bonny Coast
- Rottnest Island
- Maria Island

Dates:

Select a parameter:

Bacterial Temperature Index

Bacterial Temperature Index: Index describing the optimal temperature for a bacteria - peak kernel density.

- Tick for more microbial parameters
- Change the plot scale to log10

Trend Analysis Climatologies Trend analysis by depth

A plot of selected microbial indices from the NRS around Australia, as a time series and a monthly climatology by station averaged across all depths.

Plot Data R Code Example

<https://shiny.csiro.au/BioOceanObserver/>

A few final thoughts.....

Integration with other repositories

- [GBIF](#)
- OBIS
- Ocean Microbiomics Database
- Sandpiper
- SPIRE
- Global viral database
- Global Fungi

Integration is great, but.....

UNOFFICIAL

- INSDC
- GBIF
- OBIS

We submit and sometimes interact with

- Ocean Microbiomics Database
- Sandpiper

We interact with, they don't get it from us

- SPIRE
- Global Fungi
- Global AM Fungi

We don't interact with, they don't get it from us

- Atlas of Living Australia

We try to submit it, they don't want it

- Other databases (global atlas of soil viruses, marDB's,

Many efforts dilute impact and potential resourcing. The incentive to provide FAIR data is diminishing, NOT increasing

UNOFFICIAL

UNOFFICIAL

Looking forward.....

- **Metadata compliance is key to data re-use**
- **Attribution is important in incentivizing FAIR data, we need to do this better**
 - **people that use “free” data often seem to forget where it came from**
- **There is a real need to upskill data users in finding and interrogating data**
 - Few people want to read docs and schemas.....
 - Few people want to understand a workflow
- **Coordination and working together is difficult, but when we do the gains are much greater**
 - **Data that meets developing and future needs**
 - **Shared and therefore greater resourcing and access to resources**

UNOFFICIAL

UNOFFICIAL

Australian Microbiome

Australian Government
Parks Australia

BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA

Andrew.Bissett@csiro.au

UNOFFICIAL